

THE ROLE OF DIGITIZATION IN THE ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT: *The article discusses the importance of the digital economy, which is a modern requirement, and the benefits of its implementation in our country.*

KEYWORDS: *digital technology, digital economy, engineering, economics.*

The increase in the share of innovative activity has led to the fact that innovations are the same such as minerals, production capacity and intellectual capacity the country's wealth began to be counted. Our country and each of its citizens effective use of innovative and scientific and technical potential in the interests of formation of a multi-sectoral innovation policy in our country and its implementation to increase - there is no possibility without creating legal bases. The head of our state said, "... our country is an international information technology leader in 2019 according to the index of development of communication technologies although it has risen to the top, it is still far behind. Most ministries and agencies, It is also true that companies are far from digital technologies. Of course, Building a digital economy requires infrastructure, a lot of money and labor we know very well that it requires resources. However, no matter how difficult it is If we don't start work today, when will we start?! Tomorrow will be too late. To this end, active transition to the digital economy is one of our most important tasks in the next 5 years will be. Digital technologies not only improve the quality of products and services, but also reduce costs. At the same time, I am very worried and they are also effective in eliminating the most serious evil that bothers us - corruption is a tool. We all need to understand this deeply. State and community management, widely introducing digital technologies in the social sphere and increasing productivity, one in other words, people's lives can be dramatically improved." President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his appeals to the Oliy Majlis 2022 declared the year as the "Year of

Development of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy" It can be noted with satisfaction, pride and pride that this is an appeal not only in the guide and guide for 2020, but perhaps Uzbekistan is close. It is fundamental as a program that determines the path of development in the medium term can be considered as an important historical document. In general, any Science, including economics, and society is more important than mathematical achievements if you don't use it, you can't get high.

Relevance of the article

According to the results of various studies, the world of the digital economy its weight in the economy ranges from 4.5 to 15.5 percent. Almost of the added value created in the world information and communication technology sector 40% and 75% of patents related to blockchain technologies are American. It corresponds to the contribution of the United States and the People's Republic of China. The President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's information on February 13, 2022 the statistician gave at the event dedicated to the development of technology according to the data of the digital economy in the United States in the gross domestic product share is 10.9 percent, 10 percent in China, 5.5 percent in India. This is in Uzbekistan the indicator does not exceed 2 percent. How much the importance and impact of digitization is increasing to evaluate several major technology companies of the last decade and it is enough to see the share of capital of digital platforms in the world market. In our country, the legal system is being developed for the development of the digital economy studying propaganda;

- The place of the digital economy in the development of the countries of the world study;
- Analysis of reforms in our country in numbers;
- Expressing conclusions and suggestions.

However, in the context of the global economic crisis, enterprises and scientific groups the task of improving the efficiency of the use of allocated funds is in the first place stands. In this regard, we come across the concept of economic efficiency. For these purposes, every year in the countries of the European Union, Europe is innovative indicators (YIK) are

published. Also in 2007, one of the European Union technical efficiency based on the method of analyzing the working environment for a number of countries indicators were calculated. People of the world say that digital technologies depend on the economy 50 will dramatically change more than 100% of industries. This view is informative technologies and digital platforms dramatically change business models and their efficiency to eliminate intermediaries and optimize processes based. According to World Bank calculations, 10 of fast internet users percent increase can increase the annual GDP from 0.4 percent to 1.4 percent it is. Also, the share of the digital economy in the country's GDP is approx 20 percent growth (in developed countries this indicator is around 7 percent) is it is considered as an indicator that determines its importance. Boston Consulting in 2010. The Group's digitization rate is 2.3 for a group of 20 countries trillion dollars (4.1 percent of GDP). If this trend continues, 10-15 after the year, the share of such an economy in the world GDP will approach 30-40 percent. "Uzbektelecom" is an example of the results of the reforms carried out in our country. We can take the activity of a joint stock company. Administrative in our country simplifying the process of transition, improving the quality of life of the population, investment and including e-government aimed at improving the business environment in terms of modernization and development of the state service delivery system "Uzbekista Digital economy, e-government and information to public administration of the Republic PF-5598 "On additional measures for the introduction of systems Farmoni is a clear example of this.

Instead of conclusions and suggestions, it is worth saying that humanity is for development. It is clear only if it is carried out with the aim of making life easier the plan can be used. In the current period and near future of human development in terms of the quality of economic sectors, social sphere and state management system development is directly related to the widespread introduction of digital technologies is going. The prospect of our country's development is the development of the digital economy and relies on the level of coverage of digital technologies. To achieve this the following basic conditions and priorities

for the development of the digital economy it is appropriate to list the directions. It is no exaggeration to say that the literacy of the population is a step forward in this regard. It is the same in our country: digital technology for public literacy at leisure. At the same time, the process of training specialists in this field is being strengthened. Leading specialists are currently lacking in digitization, which is also hindering; the number of activities of total schools in the field of secondary education. If we are not connected to technology, it is difficult to see the future towards a long digital life and hard work; an enterprise that is currently operating, increasing the level of knowledge of employees, suitable for modern technical activities, incentives that create a favorable opportunity for special tests or monthly salary. If we don't use it, we will separate the techniques in this field from the breath of the past; we can't. Although the above suggestions may seem simple to you, they are actually ours that you and we can be the prelude to our foundation for future development we know well.

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